

A Case Study on Crew Resource Management and Team Building in the Aviation Technology Program of Aerospace University, Lapu-Lapu City

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Abstract

This case study delves into the impact of a team-building program implemented by an aerospace university in Lapu-Lapu City on their Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology program. Utilizing Creswell's seven-step data collection methodology, the study involved eight participants from the aviation technology program. Data was gathered through in-depth, semi-structured interviews, developed and validated by the researchers and three experts. These interviews were conducted face-to-face at the university. The data analysis revealed four key themes: participants reported enhanced relationships through shared experiences, cultivated meaningful relationships, demonstrated character development amidst financial and time-related challenges, and showcased resilience and adaptability. The study's findings highlight the positive impact of team-building activities on relationship enhancement, communication, and resilience among aviation students. To sustain and amplify these benefits, the university is encouraged to incorporate regular reflection sessions into the program. This case study provides valuable insights into the effectiveness of team-building programs in promoting the personal and academic growth of aviation technology students.

Keywords: *teambuilding, activities, aviation technology*

Introduction

Team building is a process designed to help group members work effectively together, often through engaging activities or interactive exercises (Cambridge Dictionary, 2023). In a study from the International Journal of Aviation, Aeronautics, and Aerospace (2019), several factors were identified as influencing the success of team-building exercises in aviation technology education. A key factor was the relevance of these activities to the specific challenges of the aviation industry. When exercises mirrored real-world aviation scenarios, students gained hands-on experience in critical skills such as clear communication, teamwork, and collaborative problem-solving. These activities promoted empathy, trust, creativity, and self-confidence—essential qualities for aviation professionals—and helped students develop life skills like active listening and mutual support that can't easily be learned through textbooks alone. As the American Psychological Association (2018) notes, the importance of collaboration in the workforce continues to rise.

The aviation-focused team-building program provided aviation technology students with essential skills needed for success in the industry (International Journal of Aviation, Aeronautics, and Aerospace, 2019). This program emphasized practical skills such as sound judgment, communication, and time-sensitive problem-solving, all of which are crucial for building a supportive, empathetic, and creative professional environment. Indiana Aerospace University (IAU) incorporated team building in its Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology program through its Human Factors course. However, the pandemic temporarily halted this activity due to health protocols. Edkins (2002), cited by Aguinis & Kraiger (2009), highlighted the importance of team and safety training, particularly as human errors are a leading cause of issues in aviation. Morey et al. (2002) found that many errors stem from poor team coordination, which team-building programs can address. Studies by Helmreich and Merritt (2001) have further underscored the critical role of human factors—especially communication and teamwork—in aviation safety. CRM issues, such as poor in-flight communication, lack of emergency coordination, and limited shared situational awareness, can be mitigated through targeted team-building exercises that focus on communication, decision-making, and situational awareness, ultimately enhancing safety and efficiency in aircraft operations.

This background motivated the researchers to examine the challenges in IAU's team-building program and propose a sustainability plan to ensure its long-term success.

Research Question/ Objectives

This study addresses the following research questions:

1. How do aviation students at Indiana Aerospace University experience the team-building program?
2. What challenges do these students face in participating in the university's team-building program?
3. What potential solutions could Indiana Aerospace University implement to overcome these challenges?
4. What sustainability plan can be proposed to maintain the effectiveness of the team-building program?

Methodology

This qualitative study explored the lived experiences of participants, giving voice to their stories and uncovering the essence of their shared experiences (Marshall & Rossman, 2011). Participants shared insights into the team-building program's value, challenges, and opportunities. Detailed discussions on research design, sampling, data collection, analysis, and reliability are provided below.

Research Design

The study primarily aimed to evaluate the team-building program's impact on students in an aerospace university's aviation technology program in Lapu-Lapu City and gain insights into participants' perceptions. A single-case study design was used, aligning with Yin's (2003) criteria for studying "how" and "why" questions, non-manipulable behaviors, relevant contextual factors, and unclear boundaries between phenomenon and context.

Participants/Respondents

The study targeted eight fourth-year students enrolled in Indiana Aerospace University's Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology program. Using purposive sampling, the researchers selected participants who met specific criteria: (a) enrolled in the Bachelor of Science in Aviation Technology major in Flying for the 2023-2024 academic year, (b) in their fourth year, (c) participants in team-building activities, and (d) ideally able to converse in English. The department head assisted in identifying students who met these requirements.

Instruments

The researchers used a semi-structured interview guide, specifically crafted for this study, to conduct in-depth interviews, which served as the primary data collection method. Interviewers received training before conducting interviews to maintain proficiency, and consistency in interview style was ensured through calibration sessions. Research assistants were utilized as needed, and all interviews were transcribed directly from recordings. Each participant was assigned a unique code to ensure anonymity, with all data securely stored to maintain privacy.

Procedure

Following Creswell's (2012) seven-phase data collection process, the researchers: (1) identified cases meeting the study's criteria, (2) obtained permission to conduct the research, (3) ensured participants' privacy and confidentiality, (4) began data collection promptly, (5) documented all interviews, (6) discussed field notes with participants, and (7) systematically coded and stored the data. Semi-structured, face-to-face interviews were conducted on the university campus.

Data Analysis

The data analysis followed the approach of Bradley, Curry, & Devers (2007), beginning with an initial reading of the data to understand its overall meaning. Next, coding provided a structured system to organize the data. The process involved developing a clear code structure, employing both deductive (predefined) and inductive (emerging) coding methods to capture themes. After finalizing the code structure, two or three researchers independently applied the codes and then met to resolve any differences through discussion and consensus. The reliability of coding was further ensured by involving multiple coders from the research team. The final stage involved interpreting the data to draw meaningful conclusions.

Results

Upon analyzing the transcripts from in-depth interviews about the crew resource management aspects of the team-building program conducted by an aerospace university in Lapu-Lapu City for its aviation technology students, four main themes emerged: Enhancing Relationships Through Valuable Experiences, Developing Meaningful Relationships, Character Development Amid Financial and Time Challenges, and Resilience and Adaptability Activity.

Theme 1: Enhancing Relationships Through Valuable Experiences

Building strong and meaningful relationships plays a crucial role in both personal and professional development, fostered by shared experiences, mutual understanding, and effective communication. These relationships are strengthened through team-building activities and collaborative challenges, as individuals learn to appreciate teamwork. According to Anthony Butcher (2023), such shared experiences offer opportunities for communication and emotional connection.

Several participants shared their experiences:

Participant 1 recalled,

“My personal experience was memorable because it was the first time I was part of a big group, not only with my batchmates but also with seniors, first years, second years, and third years. It was a very memorable experience.”

Participant 2 noted,

“We were able to establish a stronger relationship with my fellow teammates and classmates. We applied skills from our major subjects, like human factors. But the most important part was that we had a lot of fun.”

Participant 3 shared,

“That was one of the memorable experiences because we got to build camaraderie. It was challenging and fun, and we even had lunch at the peak of the mountain. It was exciting.”

Participant 4 emphasized,

“There was an activity where we tied someone with a rope and tugged them to help them climb. It built camaraderie and trust within our class.”

Participant 5 said,

“Team building was great, especially with the aviation community. It allowed us to practice and observe crew resource management with fellow pilots.”

Participant 6 reflected,

“I took charge as a leader during the mountain climbing activity. Trust was key, as we depended on teammates to decide the next move.”

Participant 7 described, *“It was a great experience that not only shaped our perspective on our future profession but also built friendships among student pilots.”*

Participant 8 concluded,

“It was one of the highlights of my senior high school years. I worked with students from different year levels and learned to work with diverse personalities.”

Theme 2: Developing Meaningful Relationships

Meaningful relationships create a sense of belonging and community, which enhances one's connection to their academic institution and peers. These relationships extend beyond academics, contributing to personal development and collaboration. According to Wright (2018), play and interaction during team-building activities significantly strengthen interpersonal bonds.

Here are the participants' reflections:

Participant 1 shared,

“It made me more acquainted with seniors I wasn't close with before. Now, they have a big impact on my student life.”

Participant 2 said,

“Being with my classmates and some instructors made us feel like a community. The bond we built during the team building stayed with us, and we greeted each other in school afterward.”

Participant 3 mentioned,

“The team-building activity allowed me to bond with my teammates. We were separated into teams and had to work towards a common goal, which helped improve my social skills.”

Participant 4 added,

“In our education, especially with subjects like human factors, we learn how to deal with different people and their attitudes. You can't work alone in our field; collaboration is key.”

Participant 5 expressed,

“It made me feel like I belong in the industry as an aspiring pilot.”

Participant 6 stated,

“We were able to connect by sharing experiences, creating bonds we can carry forward into the future.”

Participant 7 reflected,

“The team-building program helped us understand that becoming a pilot is not easy. It taught us to stay calm during incidents and follow safety protocols.”

Participant 8 concluded

, *“The challenges brought us closer. It was a great way for us to bond and appreciate the team-building effort prepared by our university.”*

Theme 3: Character Development Amid Financial and Time Challenges

Character development is essential in aviation, particularly for team building, as it contributes to personal growth. Emily Zini (2023) emphasizes the need for ongoing team-building activities to fully engage participants in their development.

Participants shared their experiences with challenges:

Participant 1 mentioned,

“We had some scheduling conflicts since the date was set months in advance, but we managed to rearrange other commitments to make it work.”

Participant 2 shared,

“Not everyone in our class attended due to financial issues, but most of us made it. A few classmates were left behind, and only three or four of us attended.”

Participant 3 explained,

“I didn’t have scheduling conflicts because the event was planned ahead, and the department excused us from classes. However, there was initial awkwardness as we didn’t know each other well.”

Participant 5 noted,

“We had different beliefs and working strategies, but it didn’t stop us from completing the tasks.”

Participant 7 commented,

“There were no issues affecting my participation. I fully believe in the program’s design, and I appreciate how it helps students become more confident and authentic.”

Participant 8 reflected,

“No, there were no issues. The event was planned well in advance, so we had plenty of time to prepare.”

Theme 4: Resilience and Adaptability Activity

Resilience and adaptability are vital skills for aviation students, contributing to both academic and personal growth. Resilient aviators can face challenges with a positive attitude, while adaptability enables them to succeed in varied environments. Martin et al. (2013) and Holliman et al. (2018) stress that these skills are critical for emotional well-being and achievement.

Participants shared their views on resilience and adaptability:

Participant 1 expressed,

“It was definitely worth it, especially for aviation students. The experience provided lessons that directly align with our program in aviation technology.”

Participant 2 said,

“The team-building activity was beneficial as it connected to our human factors subject. It contributed to both our personal growth and learning.”

Participant 3 suggested

, *“Each team-building program should have a variety of challenges to develop different skills in students.”*

Participant 4 recommended,

“This program should not only be for aviation students but could also benefit those in other courses.”

Participant 6 stated,

“This was the best team-building activity I’ve participated in, especially since it was tailored to our human factors course.”

Participant 7 concluded,

“One strategy that should be implemented is to encourage more students to join these team-building programs, as they offer unique experiences for aviation students to assess themselves and contribute to the team's success.”.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, it was concluded that team-building activities have played a significant role in enhancing relationships, establishing meaningful connections, fostering character development amid financial and time challenges, and cultivating resilience and adaptability in aviation technology students. The team-building activities provided shared experiences that promoted collaboration, problem-solving, and critical thinking, which laid the foundation for stronger professional relationships. These activities focused on communication and trust-building, resulting in a more cohesive network among students. Moreover, the challenges faced during the team-building process helped students develop resilience and determination, qualities that are vital for their future careers in the aerospace field.

The study also highlighted the importance of character development, especially in the face of financial and scheduling challenges. Through their participation, students developed meaningful relationships that enhanced their sense of belonging and provided support during their academic journey. Overcoming obstacles together fostered a sense of camaraderie and trust among peers, which contributed to their growth both personally and professionally. Additionally, the team-building activities instilled resilience and adaptability, preparing students to face the dynamic nature of the aviation industry with confidence.

Thus, the team-building activities have been valuable in shaping the personal and professional development of aviation technology students. The focus on relationship enhancement, communication, and resilience is commendable. To further amplify these benefits, it is recommended that regular reflection sessions be integrated into the program to allow students to evaluate their experiences and consolidate their learning. Furthermore, mentorship from experienced professionals can offer additional insights into the aviation industry, reinforcing the importance of professional connections and providing guidance on overcoming industry challenges. Continued emphasis on experiential learning, mentorship, and reflective practices will contribute to the lasting positive impact of the team-building program on students.

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